

THEORETICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MUSICAL CULTURE BASED ON A QUALITATIVE APPROACH

Bekhruz Khamidovich Boltaev

Bukhara State University Faculty of Art History
Music performance and culture teacher of the department.

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Abstract. A music teacher is considered as a necessary component of professional pedagogical culture, a necessary condition for preparing a music teacher for professional and pedagogical activities. Pedagogical creativity is effective if it is based on high professional and pedagogical competence. The effectiveness of a music teacher depends on his professional skills.

We believe that professional competence is a multifactorial phenomenon. Not only special basic scientific and methodological knowledge, abilities and skills, but also professional ones, but also work with people depend on the general culture of the teacher, his value orientations, the content of his activities and his ideas about himself as a specialist includes abilities.

Key words: music, teacher, pedagogical competence, professional, music, art, education, spiritual values, person, aesthetic taste, abilities, thinking.

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКАЯ ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ РАЗВИТИЯ МУЗЫКАЛЬНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ НА ОСНОВЕ КАЧЕСТВЕННОГО ПОДХОДА

Аннотация. Музыка имеет свое музыкальное содержание, которое уникальными средствами передает нам авторское видение окружающей действительности. Музыка-средство коммуникации, "информирующее" слушателя о вещах, находящихся за ее пределами, в своеобразной форме отражающих действительность и являющихся ее образом. Содержание в музыке-это идеальная информация, одетая в материальную форму, как в символической системе.

Ключевые слова: искусство, человек, музыка, общество, ценность, человек, эстетический вкус, способности, мышление.

Since art is the opposite of the semantic value side of human existence, with the development of Science and technology, new types of synthetic art appear. Theater, television, cinema, radio theater, where music is one of the main components. This is due to the fact that music is based on auditory perception (unlike other types), it generates objective information, its vital sound characteristics, primarily a visual plan. Therefore, the music is conditionally given visual functions. Music, like other types of art, reflects the inner world of a person, and not the outer world. "Music is the language of the heart, the sphere of feelings and Mood" [5]. The basis of musical language is the audible similarity of musical and life experience, the ideal identity of life and musical feelings. They are manifested only in intonational expression. Intonations include the state of the inner world, the meaning of speech, individual characteristics, emotional nature.

Music is "the art of intonable meaning" [1]. Therefore, he, unlike other types of art, can convey not directly the visible appearance of a person, the world, something, but the spiritual side, the inner state.

In any society, music is an integral part of everyday life, in which every member of society lives from the moment of birth and tells PEOPLE "the second channel of heredity" [4]. being an

element of the environment that influences through, it forms their consciousness, developing their specific emotional, motor and other abilities.

Music is available to man and was created for the experience he provided. But man himself is the most complex of all systems created by nature and society, in turn an element in a huge hierarchy of systems: Nature, Society, humanity, the universe, finally life itself. Music is a product of human activity and isomorphic to it as a product of a certain culture. More precisely, music is isomorphic to the culture that created it - art, religion and philosophy, science and technology, social institutions and conventions, moral values and beliefs, in a word, the "field of power" created by the holistic environment of a person.

Musical art can be interpreted from the point of view of various philosophers, researchers of the perception of music. On the one hand, music is a rational art, designed to convey specific ideas and describe specific things from the composer to the audience, and on the other hand, music is an irrational art, since it conveys only pure abstract experiences. Abstract because they are not related to a specific topic or life circumstances.

There are a number of researchers who consider music to be a specific emotional, emotional sphere of an individual who "sings" by nature.

1. Musical arts A. N. According to Sohor, one of the manifestations of musical culture, which is "the unity of music and its social activity" [6].

Musical culture has its own structure (musical values of society, all types of activities related to music, all subjects of this activity, all social institutions and institutions, musical instruments and technical equipment that serve this activity); its distinctive features (elite and mass stratification).

2. Musical art, as the essence of musical culture, performs the following functions: practical, communicative, educational, cognitive. The mechanisms of influence of musical art on the inner world of a person are determined by the music itself, its pedagogical significance.. The decisive factors in this are the philosophical categories of content and form, which act in unity in music and have a figurative embodiment. The power of musical influence is "the unity (reflection of reality) and the material form of ideal composition" [3]. It is associated with the peculiarities of the reflection of its content, expressed by musical intonations. An important aspect of music, being one of the leading musical and pedagogical problems, is primarily realized through emotional influence on a person and forms a culture of his feelings.

4. The changing power of music makes it especially significant pedagogically, indispensable in the formation of personality and the development of the spiritual potential of society. Accordingly, music affects a person, forms him as a person, indirectly affects the development of the spiritual potential of society. A. N. In his work "the educational role of music", Sohor identifies three levels of the influence of music on man.

1. Ideological. The final meaning of the content of music is the expression of any idea, so the highest influence turns out to be ideological, semantic. Deeply experienced music affects the inner world of a person, his consciousness, attitude to the surrounding life, forms moral values, views, aesthetic taste. Ideological influence is the final result of a complex process of perception and experience of music.

2. Emotional. Of all the known types of art, music has the strongest emotional impact on a person, provoking the brightest emotional response. This is explained by the similarity of musical language and speech intonations and gestures, and speech and gestures are the most powerful means of expressing emotions in real life. Music that emotionally affects a person forms a culture of emotions. Music teaches you to empathize, express your feelings aesthetically.

3. Physiological. Music can affect breathing, blood circulation, heart rhythm and other physiological processes. Russian physiologists at the end of the XIX century I. Dogel and I. Tarkhanov experimentally studied the physiological effects of music on the listener. Their experiments revealed one important feature: a meaningful sequence of musical sounds, that is, tones affect a person much more strongly than individual sounds, so the body's attitude towards music is determined by its emotional, psychological effect rather than its physiological effect [6].

In the context of the ever-increasing flow of information, the ability to direct it, the ability to assess the artistic value of a work of art and its importance for the development of the spiritual world and culture of society as a whole, the ability to artistic communication with music, the ability to resist negative manifestations of culture are important. Music has its own musical content, which conveys to us the author's vision of the surrounding reality with its own means.

Music is a means of communication, "informs" the listener about what is outside him, reflects reality in its own form and becomes his image. Content in music, as in a symbolic system, is an ideal information dressed in a material form.

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